

CHARACTERISING THE COMMUNITY: REQUIREMENTS, RESOURCES AND SKILLS

EAC AARG Survey 2023

Summary

In 2023 the EAC/AARG/ISAP joint working party on archaeological remote sensing and prospection conducted a survey to gain insight into the composition, challenges and opportunities of the community of specialists in aerial archaeology and remote sensing. 86 Individual and Institutional responses were received, representing perspectives and experiences across 29 countries with a focus on Europe and the UK. The results of the survey highlight:

- The scale of investment in staff, training and resources over the past 5 years, but a reduction in planned investments for the next 5 years compared to the previous period.
- Small, but meaningful, shortages in a range of specialist aerial archaeology and remote sensing skills in demand across the sector.
- A good match between the range of skills held by professionals and the competencies required by institutions, but a sense that university training is increasingly focused primarily on technical skills and does not sufficiently emphasise landscape interpretation skills.
- Persistent concerns that aerial archaeology and remote sensing specialist services are undervalued in the sector and consequently under resourced.
- The perception that the broader changes in the sector, notably those related to climate change impacts on land management, will impact on the work of aerial archaeology and remote sensing professionals over the next 5 years.

The survey provides baseline information, reflecting the situation in 2023, and the working party plans to repeat it in future cycles to assess progress and highlight emergent trends.

Introduction

As the work of archaeology and heritage management professionals evolves, the role of different specialisations, the skills and resources required to practice them, and how individuals and organisations contribute transforms. The European Archaeological Consilium, Aerial Archaeology Research Group, and International Society for Archaeological Prospection (EAC/AARG/ISAP) Working Party (WP), connecting the EAC, an organisation which unites professionals in heritage management, with AARG, a network of individual practitioners conducted a survey to assess the role, needs and contributions of aerial archaeology and remote sensing specialists.

The analysis of the survey results aims to provide the specialist community of practitioners with information they can use to demonstrate the value of their contribution, provide the wider archaeological community with a clearer understanding of the role of this specialist community, and to highlight trends and emergent gaps in investments in resources and skills across the community. This is the first survey designed to characterise professional activity, resource allocations, and skills in this specialist community. The information in this report provides a baseline against which to assess future trends. The survey questions, full anonymised responses, and analysed data can be found on the project's [zenodo repository](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8337802) (10.5281/zenodo.8337802).

Respondents and representativity

The EAC AARG 2023 survey was disseminated online via social media and through the mailing lists targeting the EAC and AARG membership and was open for 10 weeks from May-July 2023. Individuals were invited to respond by reporting their own views or on behalf of an institution, reporting that organisation's position.

The survey primarily reflects the situation in Europe, where most respondents, both institutional and individual are located. 86 Individual and Institutional responses received represent perspectives and experiences in 29 countries. With 2/3 of EAC member countries represented, the results of the survey are

taken to be broadly representative of international diversity across the professional community.

Institutions located in Bulgaria, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Lithuania, Malta, Norway, Portugal, the Russian Federation, Sweden, and the UK responded. Heritage management in Germany and the UK is devolved on a regional or national basis. Responses were received from England, Northern Ireland, Wales and Scotland in the UK and from Saxony, Cologne and Düsseldorf, Schleswig-Holstein, and Hesse in Germany. Individuals reported the region or country in which they primarily work (Table 1).

Table 1: Regions where individuals practice, as reported.

Albania	France	Italy	Republic of Ireland, Generally around the Dublin and Leinster
Australia	Germany (Bavaria)	Midlands and East of England (based in Shropshire)	Spain
Bohemia	Germany, (Rheinladpfalz + Rheinhessen) few surveys in Spain, Portugal, Tunisia	Minneapolis, MN USA	Switzerland
Croatia	Germany, North Rhine-Westphalia	Netherlands	Turkey
Czech Republic	Hesse, Germany	Norway	Turkey, Syria, Iraq
Denmark	Hungary	Norway, Rogaland, Stavanger	UK
England	International	Poland	USA
Europe	Ireland/Northern Ireland	Portugal	

Who Responded

32 Institutions
from 15 Countries

55 Individuals
from 19 Countries

Responses by Institutions

Responses by Individuals
- Europe

Responses by Individuals
- Global

Figure 1: Maps of responses by institutions and individuals, with a focus on Europe as the main region of interest.

Academic, commercial /development-led, and cultural heritage management organisations make up roughly equal parts of the responses from institutions. However, in Europe and the UK there are over 200 Universities offering archaeology degrees and well over 1000 independent archaeological contractors and commercial / development-led organisations (see Aitchinson, German and Rocks-MacQueen 2021 for UK numbers which provide a minimum basis). Evidently, the responses represent a very small part of the sector overall and their proportions don't match overall demographics in the wider sector, and consequently should be interpreted cautiously when considering the scale of resources or distribution of skills across the sector.

Table 2: Number of institutional responses received per type of organisation.

# institutions	Institution type	# individuals	Individual role
7	academic research	22	researcher
13	commercial / development-led archaeology	24	commercial archaeologist
10	cultural heritage management	3	heritage manager
1	environmental management	4	teacher
1	Government's statutory advisor on the historic environment	1	retired

60% of respondents are AARG members and engage in an international professional membership organisation.

METHODS NOTE

When analysing individual responses, locations were aggregated on a per country basis to match the institutional responses. If multiple countries were reported, a best guess at the primary country of practice was made based on contextual information from the response and the categories of 'Europe' and 'International' were excluded. When comparing individual and institutional responses, it is important to note this may not be the same as the region or country where the individual primarily resides, especially for academic respondents. Those responding on behalf of an organisation could also submit a separate response as an individual. Because responses were anonymised, it is not possible to report how many responses were received from an individual who also responded on behalf of their organisation.

In what situations are aerial archaeology and remote sensing used?

Institutions' statements of their current applications of aerial archaeology and remote sensing (AARS) provide a basic picture of the activities and types of projects where these specialist skills and data are required. The most common requirement is for the creation of data (site identification, monitoring, interpretation), closely followed by a role supporting other archaeological work either during planning or fieldwork stage. Use as a part of reporting is common,

while only a few organisations (<25%) reported uses for public engagement activities.

Figure 2: Current types of activities and projects where institutions use remote sensing and aerial archaeology.

In interpreting the reported results, the low level of reported use in public engagement suggests that respondents may be making a distinction between using aerial archaeology and remote sensing as a source of data or information and using aerial and remotely sensed imagery for illustrations. Anecdotally, it is common to see an aerial image or a map overlaid on a satellite image as part of the materials provided in a public engagement activity. That this doesn't 'count' in the minds of respondents may point to the emergence of a general distinction between images as illustrations and images as data that has emerged in archaeology and heritage management over the past 20 years.

Required vs available resources

To meet the needs of their AARS applications, institutions have made and plan a range of investments. The survey asked organisations to report on the types of investments in resources made in the last and planned for the coming 5 years. The frequency of investment in a category is interpreted as an indicator of its importance across the community. The survey did not request details on the scale of investment, e.g. number of purchases or amount spent, because of the difficulty interpreting this data in a way that would sensitively reflect diverse local contexts. While this limits the robustness of the interpretation, several key trends emerge.

- Less investment in resources in every category is planned for the next 5 years compared to the previous period, apart from infrastructure investments. This trend may reflect a lack of certainty or even pessimism regarding spending in the next 5 years or may reflect a real planned reduction in resources.
- While organisations value infrastructure resources, individual practitioners don't view these as important investments.
- While organisations are making investments in data resources, individual practitioners view greater access to data as an ongoing need.
 - The predicted decrease in investment in data may reflect a growing availability of data under government and open licenses.
- Investment in and requirements for training are currently well matched and this looks set to continue for the next 5 years.
- The number of institutions investing in staff is set to dip by roughly 1/3, a significant change in a small specialism.

Figure 3: Comparing individual views on resource requirements with planned and past investments by institutions reveals general trends in priorities across the AARS specialism and wider sector.

REGIONAL TRENDS

Within Europe and the UK, the resources prioritised for investment vary significantly. The UK and Ireland are seen to invest broadly across all resource types. Investment in selected categories across the rest of the European area may reflect real differences in priorities and constraints, or may represent cyclical change, e.g. a country which hired several people 7 years ago may report low hiring in the past 5 years if staff turnover is low. The lack of investment in training in South-Eastern Europe may reflect a reliance on international training programmes based elsewhere.

Past Investments

Future Investments

Figure 4: Reported past and future resource investments vary significantly across Europe and the UK.

Skills

SKILLS IN DEMAND TODAY

To assess the match between skills required in the sector and the current skillsets of practitioners, institutions and individuals were asked to select from a single list of key skills. Institutions were asked to report on the skills related to aerial archaeology and remote sensing prioritised when recruiting staff and supporting ongoing professional development, while individuals were asked to describe their specialisation and expertise. While the rank position of specific skills frequently differed by a few places between skills held by individuals and those required by institutions, the skills prioritised match very well overall, with 9 out of 10 skills appearing in both groups top list.

Table 3: The skills most frequently mentioned by institutions and individuals overlap substantially for the top 5 skills and almost entirely when considering the top 10 skills. Matched skills are coded in the same colour and skills are listed in descending rank position.

top 10 held skills	top 10 required skills
Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: Visual image interpretation	GIS: map creation and editing
Integration with fieldwork	GIS: data management
GIS: map creation and editing	Integration with fieldwork
Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: georeferencing and image rectification	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: Visual image interpretation
UAV imagery and/or data processing	Integration of aerial archaeology and remote sensing into wider project management
GIS: data management	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: georeferencing and image rectification
Integration of aerial archaeology and remote sensing into wider project management	UAV imagery and/or data processing
GIS: geospatial analysis e.g. analysis of spatial autocorrelation	GIS: geospatial analysis e.g. analysis of spatial autocorrelation
Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: identifying relevant data sources	UAV operation and data acquisition in the field
Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: basic data analysis e.g. calculating vegetation indices, producing lidar visualisations	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: identifying relevant data sources

While there is a good match between the skills prioritised by institutions and the ones professionals have, two important gaps between skills in supply and in demand emerge on closer inspection of the data. First, several of the top 10 key skills are mentioned more frequently as a required skill than as a held skill, suggesting there may be a slight shortage of individuals with the necessary skillsets. This trend is most pronounced in relation to basic GIS skills, but it is possible that individuals are under-reporting what they perceive to be generalist skills.

Table 4: The skills gap represents the difference between the frequency with which a skill is held by an individual and required by an institution. Gaps over 1% are coded orange and gaps within 1% are coded green.

held skills		required skills		gap
GIS: map creation and editing	6.33%	GIS: map creation and editing	8.75%	- 2.43%
GIS: data management	5.44%	GIS: data management	7.74%	- 2.30%
GIS: metadata creation	2.91%	GIS: metadata creation	4.38%	- 1.47%
Other	1.14%	Other	2.36%	- 1.22%
Integration with fieldwork	6.46%	Integration with fieldwork	7.41%	- 0.95%
Community outreach- use of Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery	2.41%	Community outreach- use of Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery	3.03%	- 0.63%
UAV mounted geophysical data collection	1.27%	UAV mounted geophysical data collection	1.68%	- 0.42%
Specialist Report Production incorporating Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery	2.66%	Specialist Report Production incorporating Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery	3.03%	- 0.37%
Integration of aerial archaeology and remote sensing into wider project management	5.44%	Integration of aerial archaeology and remote sensing into wider project management	5.72%	- 0.28%
Scripting (e.g. python)	1.65%	Scripting (e.g. python)	1.68%	- 0.04%

A more meaningful gap appears when considering the geographic distribution of skills required and held. Because knowledge of the character of local archaeological features and landscapes, together with knowledge of national and regional legislation, is often a desired if not required qualification for a role, international mobility in specialist roles at a more senior level may be limited. With this in mind, disparities at a national level mean that the gap between the number of skilled individuals and roles available may be larger than suggested by the aggregated data.

Skills held by Individuals

- Integration with fieldwork
- Community outreach-use of Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery
- Specialist Report Production incorporating Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery
- Integration of aerial archaeology and remote sensing into wider project management
- UAV mounted geophysical data collection

Institutionally reported skills needs

- Integration with fieldwork
- Community outreach-use of Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery
- Specialist Report Production incorporating Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery
- Integration of aerial archaeology and remote sensing into wider project management
- UAV mounted geophysical data collection

It is also notable that the skills prioritised vary by organisation size, potentially reflecting the different character of projects taken on in small or specialist organisations and larger organisations providing a wider range of services. The skills most valued also vary between the public (heritage management) and academic sectors, a disparity that potentially creates challenges both for professionals seeking to change their career to a new organisation type and for organisations seeking to fill specialist roles.

Table 5: Skills prioritised by commercial / development-led organisations.

small commercial		medium commercial		large commercial	
Integration with fieldwork	10.77%	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: advanced data analysis e.g. multi-temporal analysis, change detection, point cloud processing tasks such as classification	11.11%	GIS: data management	9.68%
GIS: map creation and editing	9.23%	GIS: geospatial analysis e.g. analysis of spatial autocorrelation	11.11%	Integration with fieldwork	9.68%
Integration of aerial archaeology and remote sensing into wider project management	7.69%	GIS: data management	11.11%	GIS: map creation and editing	9.68%
GIS: data management	7.69%	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: georeferencing and image rectification	7.41%	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: identifying relevant data sources	6.45%

Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: basic data analysis e.g. calculating vegetation indices, producing lidar visualisations	6.15%	Integration with fieldwork	7.41%	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: image acquisition	6.45%
Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: Visual image interpretation	6.15%	GIS: map creation and editing	7.41%	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: georeferencing and image rectification	6.45%

Table 6: Skills prioritised by academic organisations differ from those prioritised by public institutions, potentially introducing challenges for specialists seeking to move across the sector or for organisations looking to fill open roles.

top academic skills	top commercial skills	top public institution skills		
Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: advanced data analysis e.g. multi-temporal analysis, change detection, point cloud processing tasks such as classification	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: advanced data analysis e.g. multi-temporal analysis, change detection, point cloud processing tasks such as classification	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: identifying relevant data sources		skills prioritised at a higher level in academia
Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: basic data analysis e.g. calculating vegetation indices, producing lidar visualisations	GIS: data management	Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: Visual image interpretation		skills prioritised at a higher level in industry and the public sector
Aerial, lidar, and satellite RS imagery: Visual image interpretation	GIS: geospatial analysis e.g. analysis of spatial autocorrelation	GIS: data management		
GIS: data management	GIS: map creation and editing	GIS: geospatial analysis e.g. analysis of spatial autocorrelation		
GIS: map creation and editing	Integration of aerial archaeology and remote sensing into wider project management	GIS: map creation and editing		
UAV imagery and/or data processing	Integration with fieldwork	GIS: metadata creation		

SKILLS FUTURES

Individuals were given the opportunity to comment on the skills most needed in the aerial archaeology and remote sensing sector in their country. Their responses highlight a set of skills with growing importance and point toward future trends and training needs. Synthesising multiple responses, key emergent skills include:

- Development of bespoke methods and algorithms
- Providing training in how to use the datasets
- Coordination of different specialisations (archaeology and technical)
- Connecting aims of projects to the choice of technology used
- Technical interpretation and analysis skills
- UAV generalist skills
- Big Data management - specialists and services that leverage novel GIS and remote (cloud) file architectures

“PROFESSIONAL REMOTE SENSING DEPENDS ON FUNDING COMING FROM BEING POLITICALLY DESIRABLE. OUR WORK, AT PRESENT, IS NOT VIEWED AS SUFFICIENTLY POLITICALLY DESIRABLE.” - *GERMANY*

Reflections on the state of AARS work

While institutional responses were focused on metrics around priorities, investments and skills requirements, individual responses allowed for more discursive comments on the state of AARS in different countries. These comments highlight potential explanations for some of the gaps in resourcing and skills identified through the survey and point toward future actions for the AARS professional community.

The perception that AARS is undervalued and, consequently, under resourced, persists. Archaeology and heritage management increasingly prioritise impact

and public benefits, and new ways of framing of the results of AARS, typically revealing features or patterns of features not visible to people standing in the landscape, in this context are needed to convey its results as exciting, desirable, and valuable. In parallel, within some professional circles, assessments made

“IN SHORT, REMOTE SENSING IN GENERAL IS NOT WIDELY ACCEPTED AS A TRUSTWORTHY METHOD FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE MANAGEMENT YET. THEREFORE, WE ARE IN MANY CASES LACKING FUNDS AND RESOURCES.” -
NORWAY

based on non-invasive prospection methods continue to be viewed as less robust, and consequently less valuable, than those made through excavation.

The key to attracting more resource and positive attention to AARS, as expressed by one respondent is to make, “more people to be interested - assuming 'people' are a resource,” addressing the challenge that,

“archaeology is [] seen as mainly digging holes”.

Attracting archaeologists with the capacity to work in positions where they can influence resource allocation to specialise in AARS is one means of addressing this challenge. Here, the emphasis on technical skills during training, while essential to building the competence to carry out AARS tasks, may inadvertently lead to the perception that these roles are exclusively specialist technician roles, rather than mainstream archaeologist roles.

As stated by one respondent, “While there is an abundance of people who can operate equipment, there are fewer and fewer who could take the process through from desk-based assessments, who could create and integrate remote sensing data and who could then use that information in the field to deliver or even manage effective fieldwork. Universities appear to be training students in narrower areas of digital data processing and we are not producing people with the required balance of skills and experience where field skills are combined with spatial digital skills.” A more holistic approach, emphasising interpretive and broader heritage management skills, together with technical capabilities, may help to re-centre AARS specialists within the professional community. Further examples of AARS work which successfully informed interpretations,

together with initiatives to gather evidence of the scale and diversity of AARS's contributions, may provide further tools for continuing advocacy for the value of AARS.

“LEADERSHIP - CLEAR DIRECTION AND DRIVE FROM ORGANISATIONS [...] TO TACKLE THE BIG DATA ISSUES.” - *UK*

Future Directions

The 2023 survey provides an initial picture of the composition, challenges, and opportunities of the aerial archaeology and remote sensing specialist community. As remote sensing technologies and the data required for landscape heritage work continue to evolve, including the growth in use of big data, cloud storage architectures, and increased diversity and quality of remote sensing data, the community faces continued challenges balancing investments in specialist technical expertise with archaeological expertise. Growing emphasis on the integration of heritage management with other aspects of land management in the context of climate change is likewise starting to impact the practice of AARS, as priorities for assessment of landscapes and the volume of work shifts. In this context, information on the AARS professional community can be used to consider:

- How can aerial and remote sensing methods become more trusted, valued, and integrated across archaeological and heritage work?
- What internal paradigm shifts might the AARS community need to make as the broader context of archaeological and heritage work changes?
- How can the international community support practitioners in different countries to advocate for AARS in their local context?
- How can the AARS community advocate for itself effectively, internally within archaeology and heritage and to organisations in other sectors?
- How can specialist training, peer mentoring and ongoing professional development be supported across the community?

To build our understanding of the development of this specialism as an area of professional practice, the EAC/AARG/ISAP WP plan to conduct similar surveys

in future years, enabling the identification of trends and reflecting on changes in practice of aerial archaeology and remote sensing.

REFERENCES

Aitchison, K., German, P., & Rocks-Macqueen, J.D. 2021. *Profiling the Profession 2020*. DOI: 10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.14333387.#

EAC/AARG/ISAP WP Zenodo Repository
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8337801>